

Ensuring Canine Health: The Vital Role of Vaccination and Deworming

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A puppy's immature immune system makes it susceptible to infection when it is first born. Thankfully, moms create colostrum, a unique type of milk, in the initial days following birth. All of the mother's antibodies are abundant in colostrum. The puppies will be absorbing their mother's immunity as they consume this milk. The mother's antibodies disappear by the time the puppy is 16 to 20 weeks old, so it must continue to develop its own immune system. Through vaccinations, your puppy can develop immunity against common illnesses that could damage them. Pets have increased risk of diseases as they are susceptible to various organisms in the environment directly or indirectly. Vaccinating your pet is much economical than treating them post-infection. The common diseases against which the pets are vaccinated include – Rabies, Infectious Canine Hepatitis, Canine Distemper, Parvovirus and Leptospirosis.

Vaccination Schedule

After the birth, the puppy receives the maternal antibodies through colostrum (i.e., First mother's milk) and is protected by these maternal antibodies that last for a few weeks. However, this temporary maternal protection wanes by the age of 6–9 weeks. To continue and enhance this protection, vaccinations are a must.

Age of Puppy	Type of Vaccination
4 th Week	Puppy DP vaccine
6 th Week	DHPPiL vaccine
9 th Week	DHPPiL vaccine booster
12 th Week	Antirabies vaccine
15 th Week	Antirabies vaccine booster
Annually	DHPPiL + Antirabies vaccine

The first vaccine that is generally given is the “Puppy DP” at 4 weeks of age. This protects the puppy from deadly life-threatening viruses i.e., Parvo (acquired through physical contact) and Distemper (direct contact/ airborne). At 6th week of age, a combined cluster of vaccines commonly known as 5-in-1, 7-in-1, 9-in-1 or 11-in-1 is given with a Booster Shot after 21 days. These protect your puppy from viruses such as Adenovirus, Parvovirus, Distemper, Leptospira, and some other deadly diseases, which can be fatal for the puppy. Don't be confused about which vaccine cluster is the best. There is a base level protection against five diseases and in the rest of the vaccines; there is increased protection against more strains of Leptospira. 9-in-1 and 11-in-1 also provide protection against Coronavirus. At 12th week of age an anti-rabies vaccine is given to protect the puppy against the deadly rabies. Remember to give a booster shot of anti-rabies after 21 days. Vaccinate your dog annually with the combined cluster vaccine and anti-rabies.

Important things to remember about Pet Vaccinations

- One of the most important things to remember is to “REMEMBER TO VACCINATE ON TIME”. I would recommend you to set a reminder for every annual vaccination.
- Vaccines should not be administered if the pet is suffering from fever or any other poor health condition. Vaccines must be given to healthy dog only.
- Maintaining vaccination record is absolutely critical, so be meticulous about storing your Vaccination Certificates and records. With that, don't forget to collect the Bottle Sticker of any Vaccination that is administered to your pet. This puts on

record the Vaccine Company and Batch Number of the Vaccine for future reference.

- Deworm your pet one week before first vaccination.

De-worming schedule

It is important to ensure that a de-worming schedule is adhered to, in order to prevent harmful parasites from affecting your pet. When these parasites are allowed to grow, there will be a host of health complications.

The following is a suggested schedule for eradicating worms (check with your veterinarian for clarifications and ways to identify a worm infestation).

- Start deworming your pups at 3 weeks of age.
- Deworming should be done every fortnight up to the age of 3 months.
- After 3 months and up to 6 months of age deworming is done once a month.
- Once in 2 months for puppies between 6 and 12 months of age.
- After 1 year of age, keep a routine practice of deworming your dog at least once in 3 to 6 months.

“Pets are a responsibility, not a hobby”